

Contribution of Artificial Intelligence to Publishing in Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: This study explores the contributions of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to the publishing industry in Nigeria, focusing on its potential to enhance various aspects of the publishing process.

Method: The study utilized secondary data sources, including books, journals, and online materials, to gather relevant information. The key objectives were to identify areas where AI can be applied in publishing and to examine its contributions to the industry.

Findings/Results: The study identified key areas where AI can assist publishing, including referencing, proofreading, peer review, and editing. AI contributes to

publishing in Nigeria by generating book content, improving content quality, optimizing resource allocation, enhancing title distribution, translating books into multiple Nigerian languages, reducing production time and costs, and increasing revenue for the industry.

Implications: AI adoption in publishing benefits both publishers and readers by improving efficiency, content quality, and accessibility while generating higher revenue for the industry.

Conclusion: AI significantly enhances the publishing industry in Nigeria, benefiting publishers through increased revenue and readers through access to high-quality books.

Recommendations: Publishers should compensate employees who lose jobs due to AI adoption, particularly those with a history of dedication, by offering retraining programs to prepare them for new roles created by AI advancements.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Book, Mass Media, Nigeria, Publishing

Introduction

Publishing in the true sense started when Johannes Gutenberg in 1440-1450 invented the moveable metal type, resulting in mass production of printed materials. Since then, the world has witnessed a lot of transformations. One of such transformation was the development of the Internet, which gave birth to Information Communication Technology, leading to the production of book in electronic format called e- book.

Information Communication Technology has expanded its scope of influence on human society with the development of Artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence, a branch of Information Communication Technology focuses on developing systems which has the ability to perform tasks that requires human intelligence. Artificial intelligence has the capabilities computers have to display intelligence

that is normally exhibited in humans, by utilising algorithm to analysis data, learn from it, and to make decisions. Artificial intelligence has the ability to speed up the process of doing things, with resultant effect on businesses and organisations that deployed its use (Wilson, Wilson & Moses, 2019).

Artificial intelligence can be deployed in many fields to aid man in carrying out difficult or not too easy tasks. According to Deng (2018) artificial intelligence enable people to go from their old world where people give computers rules to solve problems to a new world where people get solutions to their problems from computers through machine learning by using a set of algorithms. Wooldridge (2021) writes that ...”artificial intelligence is build machines that are conscious, self-aware, and sentient, machines capable of the kind of intelligent autonomous action that currently only people are capable of.” Hamet & Tremblay (2017) describe artificial intelligence as “the use of a computer to model intelligent behavior and minimal human intervention. Artificial intelligence is a tool that can be used to improve performance and to solve complex problems”.

Application of Artificial intelligence can have impact in different fields, by using expert system, which is widely used to solve complex problems in different areas of science, engineering, business, medicine, weather forecasting, and others (Pannu,2015), thereby bringing quality, efficiency and productivity to these sectors.

Publishing is another field in which Artificial intelligence has made great strides. For instance, since 2019, Springer Nature published the world’s first machine generated research book and also conducted trials on Artificial intelligence to translate or summarise scientific publications, to match research papers with suitable peer reviewers and to detect plagiarism (Research Information, 2023). Penguin Random House, have used Artificial intelligence for years, to set the price of eBooks and to print hardcopy books (Bertelsmann, 2023).

Artificial intelligence can be of benefit to the publishing industry in Nigeria and in the developing nations in many ways. Nigeria like many nations of the world has made efforts in the adoption and use of Artificial Intelligence for national

development. This is evident in the formulation of policies that relates to the use of technology. Two of such policies are the Nigeria Data Protection Act, 2023, and the National Information Technology Agency setup by the Federal Government in 2001, which are both supported by the establishment of implementing and regulatory bodies, The Nigeria Data Protection Commission (NDPC) and National Information Technology Agency respectively, to provided guidelines on the use of technology for national development, which Artificial intelligence fall into.

A few scholars in the field of communication, like Onoja,(2023), Afolabi (2024), and Igwe (2021), have written on writing and Artificial intelligence in Nigeria, but none have written on the contribution of Artificial Intelligence to publishing in Nigeria. The purpose of this study therefore is to fill this gap. The study will be anchored on the following objectives;

- i. to identify areas where Artificial intelligence can be used in publishing
- ii. to examine how Artificial Intelligence can contribute to publishing

It is in the light of these, that the paper examines the contribution of Artificial intelligence to publishing in Nigeria, with focus on book publishing. The reason for this is that, firstly, books take longer time to produce compare to other forms of publications, therefore using Artificial intelligence will benefit book publication more than other forms of publication, as it will speed up the process of producing books. Secondly, Artificial intelligence is what is currently trending around the globe. Many industries are adopting it use, even though not fully developed, will in the near future be applied to almost every human task, to lower cost, ensure quality, efficiency, productivity and speed in getting things done.

This study examines the contribution of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to the publishing industry in Nigeria. With increasing global adoption of AI technologies, it has become essential to explore how these innovations are transforming publishing processes, especially in developing countries like Nigeria. The study focuses on identifying the areas where AI can be integrated into publishing and assessing its overall impact on the industry

Methodology

The study employed a qualitative approach using secondary data sources. Relevant information was gathered from books, academic journals, and credible online materials. These sources provided insights into the applications and benefits of AI in the publishing sector, with particular reference to the Nigerian context.

Conceptual Clarification

Artificial intelligence was mentioned in the summer of 1956, when John McCarthy known as the father of Artificial intelligence, first define the term, at a conference in Dartmouth, where the subject caught the attention of researchers (Benko & Lanyi, 2009). According to Encyclopaedia Britannica (2025) Artificial intelligence is the ability of a digital computer or computer-controlled robot to perform tasks commonly associated with people. The term is frequently applied to the project of developing systems endowed with the intellectual process characteristic of humans, such as ability to reason, discover meaning, generalise, or learn from past experience. For instance, corporations, such as Apple, Google, and Amazon are at the forefront of using artificial intelligence in their product launches and acquiring AI-based startups (Agrawal, Gans and Goldfarb, 2017).

Today you cannot talk about Artificial intelligence without mentioning OpenAI, a major player in the industry. OpenAI developed a model called chatGPT, the chatbot is the biggest in the industry (Milmo, 2025). Other chatbots are; Claude (Anthropic) developed by a former employee of OpenAI, Meta AI (Meta) was founded by Mark Zuckerberg, Gemini founded by Google, Grok (XAI) was founded by Elon Musk, another chatbot is DeepSeek, the Chinese chatbot launched in January, 2025 (Baptista, 2025). And Hunyuan, a chatbot launched recently, another Chinese company, called Tencent, to compete with DeepSeek (Deppen 2025). All these are models of Artificial intelligence developed by different players in the industry.

ChatGPT model is based on GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer) technology and it is capable of doing more than answering not too difficult

questions. It can also carried out more advanced request, leveraging on its huge data stores and efficient design (Kirmani, 2022)..

Artificial intelligence is a technical innovation that is expected to replace the manual work performed by human in various field. It is an innovation that is designed to mimic various functions which humans can do. Artificial intelligence involves the use of external data which has the capacity to achieve excellent result, when applied to a given task (Anjila, 1984).

In the near future, Artificial intelligence will profoundly impact the way we do things, in the working place, wage war, engage in sporting activities, seek a mate, educate our young ones, and care for the elderly in our society. Many foresee Artificial intelligence to increase the number of the wealthy in the society, reduce the number jobs in the labour markets, change the way things are done and this is likely to affect our private and public institutions in a negative way (Kaplan, 2016). He, further explained that “eventually it may alter how we see our place in the universe, as machines pursue goals independent of their creators and outperform us in domains previously believed to be the sole dominion of humans”. One of the challenges of Artificial intelligence is its ability to go out of control, becoming a problem for its creator man. This calls for ethical standard in the use of Artificial intelligence.

Many people have lost their jobs due to revolutionary nature that Artificial intelligence has brought to many industries. Jobs hitherto requiring human intelligence to solve, are now being performed by artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence can solve complex scientific and engineering problems through simulating, supplementing, or adding human intelligence in an efficient and precise manner (Muthukrishnan, Maleki, Owens, Reinhold, Forghani, Forghani, 2020). Artificial intelligence cannot work effectively and efficiently without the assistance of human.

Therefore, Artificial intelligence requires collaborative effort in form of skills, such as being able to explain itself to the users. On the other hand, the introduction of Artificial intelligence also requires new skills that human experts need to be

developed in order to deal with Artificial intelligence (Schraagen & Diggelen, 2021). Without developing new skills to control the use of Artificial intelligence, it may turn out to be a weapon that will eliminate the human race. Man is designed by God to work, a machine taking over this role is likely to create problem for the human race.

Publishing

The invention of moveable type by Johannes Gutenberg made mass production and distribution of printed materials possible. Nyeko (1999:1) described publishing as “the process of producing for dissemination, books, films, computer programmes, records, newspapers, periodicals, discs, bulletins, magazines and other literacy materials.” From the above definition, one can conclude that publishing is a process that seeks to garner man’s intellectual activity and storing same for the information, education, mobilisation, and entertainment using various media to make them available to the members of the society.

Book was the first medium of mass communication, newspaper followed and later magazine. All these are product of publishing. According to Akpoko (2012:27) book publishing “simply means to have a book or periodical printed out and distributed for sale.” He pointed out that publishing normally covers a wide range of activities, which include production of reports, books, newspaper , magazines and other reading materials for the use of the members of the society. Oso, Osunbiyi and Biobaku (2008) explained that publishing is a generic term used to describe the process of producing literary and information materials that are beneficial to the members of the society. Okwilagwe (2001:1) quated Chandler Grannis (1967) who defines publishing as: “to make public - to send forth among the people - the words and pictures the creative minds have produced, that editors have worked over, and that printers have reproduced”.

From the above definition, publishing can be said to be a process that involved capturing ideas from people’s creative minds and storing same in a medium with the intention of sharing such ideas to the public at a price. Okwilongwe (2001) opine that publishing consist of planning, selecting, editing, designing, producing, marketing, distribution and sales of printed materials such as books, magazines

and newspapers. In other words, publishing can also be said to be the business of producing and making available for sales, books, newspapers, magazines and other printed materials.

Books and other printed materials are also available in electronic formats. With the advent of internet, publishing has expanded to include digital information made available in the form of digital media. This type of publishing is called e-publishing (Vermilyen, 2002). E-publishing includes e-books, print-on-demand and open access publications (Mohan, 2001). Affum (2022) observed that e-publishing differs from the traditional publishing, in their form and process through which printing of e-publications take place. Bharti and Raj (2012) said, in e-publishing, documents are stored electronically, then send to a network, and printed when needed. One of the advantages of this type of publishing is that, it does not have any environmental impact, as it does not required the cutting down of trees and the use of ink or gum, which may contain chemicals that are harmful to the environment.

Conceptual framework

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stages of the publishing process. Natural Language Processing (NLP) powers tools like Grammarly and Quillbot, which improve manuscript language quality by offering real-time grammar, style, and clarity suggestions, while also aiding in automated formatting to meet journal guidelines. Machine Learning (ML) underpins recommendation systems and AI-based peer review tools, enabling smart reviewer assignments by matching manuscripts to experts based on content analysis and past reviewer performance. Generative AI models, such as ChatGPT or Claude, assist authors in drafting abstracts, generating metadata, and even creating initial content drafts, while AI-powered plagiarism detection tools ensure originality by scanning texts against vast databases. These capabilities collectively enhance efficiency and quality, forming the foundation for AI's impact on publishing.

The influence of AI capabilities manifests through mediating factors in the publishing process, which act as conduits for operational improvements. For instance, NLP and generative AI boost manuscript preparation efficiency by automating language polishing and metadata generation, ensuring submissions are well-structured and discoverable. ML-driven editorial workflow automation accelerates reviewer assignment and decision support, reducing bottlenecks in peer review. AI-based plagiarism detection and quality assurance tools strengthen credibility by flagging unoriginal content and inconsistencies early. Additionally, automated production formatting and proofing minimize manual effort in finalizing manuscripts, while AI-driven journal selection tools help authors target suitable venues, increasing acceptance rates. These process enhancements create a more efficient, accurate, and accessible publishing pipeline, directly shaping downstream outcomes.

The culmination of AI's contributions is evident in improved publishing outcomes, which reflect both direct and indirect influences of AI capabilities and process factors. Increased publication speed results from automated workflows and faster manuscript preparation, enabling journals to handle higher submission volumes. Improved manuscript quality, driven by NLP tools and rigorous plagiarism checks, enhances credibility and reader trust. Enhanced metadata generation boosts discoverability and indexing in academic databases, leading to higher citation rates and research impact. AI democratizes publishing by supporting non-native English

speakers and early-career researchers, fostering wider author participation. Reduced publication costs stem from automation, while ethical and transparent publishing is reinforced by AI's ability to detect biases and ensure originality. A feedback loop emerges as these outcomes generate more data for training AI models, further refining tools and perpetuating a cycle of innovation in publishing.

Publishing in Nigeria

Publishing in Nigeria could be said to be more than 175 years old. This is because the first printing press was established in Nigeria in 1846. According to Omu (1978) the first printing press was sited in Calabar by the Presbyterian Mission, leading to the believe that the press at that period was devoted to publishing religious materials (Kalejaye & Akangbe, 2007). Publishing in Nigeria has the same profile like any other book industry in other clime; the publishing chain is represented by the publishers, authors, editors, printers, booksellers and readers. Presently there is no accurate book production output in Nigeria, however, it is estimated that book output of the registered publishers in Nigeria is 18 million per year. These include 3 million produced outside the country (Tiamiyu, 2005). With the assistance of Artificial intelligence Nigerian book output can accurately be measured and also help to project the future Nigerian book requirements.

The dominant publishing houses in Nigeria are; Oxford University Press established in 1949, Heinemann Educational Books (Nigeria) PLC, established in 1962, Macmillan Nigeria Publishers Limited was established in 1965, Evans Brothers Nigeria Publishers Limited, Longman Nigeria PLC were established in 1966 and University of Ibadan press in 1949, which is an indigenous publishing house (Adesanoye, 2005). All these publishing houses with the exception of University of Ibadan Press were subsidiaries of British companies that were nationalized as a result of the indigenisation decree of 1972.

Another indigenous publishing house is Onibonje publishers, located in Ibadan, the Oyo state capital. The publishing house has published 800 titles since inception in 1958. These titles also include indigenous languages, which is 60% of the total book output from the company (James, 2011). Artificial intelligence can be used

more effectively and efficiently in translating books in English language into indigenous Nigerian languages.

The Nigerian publishing industry is faced with many challenges. According to Oyeyinka, Aganbi & Adebayo (2016) “the Nigerian publishing industry is characterized by poor financing, government regulation, poor reading culture, piracy and dearth of expertise” Publishing in Nigeria is largely driven by private individuals, with little or no support from government and financial institutions. However, Sawyer-George, Batubo & Afamakuro (2017) opine that piracy and preference for imported books were the challenges facing publishing houses in Nigeria. While Ifatureti cited in James (2011) was of the opinion that a high percentage of the books produced in Nigeria do not meet internationally accepted standards in physical and visual quality or in quality of content. Artificial intelligence can assist the publishing industry to improving the quality, both the physical and visual quality of books produced and the quality of book contents.

In spite of the millions of books produced by the publishing houses in Nigeria, the country’s book requirements are still below what is being produced. According to Tihamiyu, (2005) Nigeria has an estimated 166 million book requirements and Nigeria does not have the production capacity to meet this need. Nigeria’s book requirements can be met with the application of Artificial intelligence by the Nigerian publishing industry. Advantages of using Artificial intelligence in publishing are, in content development, and the speed and efficiency in which these contents are turned into books. Therefore, Artificial intelligence has the capability to meet Nigerian book requirements, as more money would be generated for the publishers and authors. This will encourage more authors to develop manuscripts that can be turned into books.

Nigeria is one of the nine countries with the largest concentration of illiterates in the world, as a large percentage of the population are still illiterates (Ogunleye, 2005). The use of Artificial intelligence to create awareness of the importance of books to a society will help imbibe reading culture, this will lead to large patronage of books by Nigerians.

Artificial Intelligence and Publishing

Many industries today are increasingly introducing Artificial intelligence into their operations. This is largely due to the improvement it is said to bring to these organisations. The Publishing industry is not left out in this new scramble to embrace the use of Artificial intelligence.

Artificial intelligence can greatly speed up the process of writing and editing manuscripts or articles, allowing both the authors and researchers to focus on the work itself rather than spending long hours on writing manuscripts and formatting them (Curtis, 2023). A book usually takes one to two years to write and publish, compare to newspapers and magazines. Applying Artificial intelligence to manuscripts or content development will accelerate publication of books and other printed materials. Artificial intelligence when fully harnessed can produce an entire article in minutes with minimal prompting from the author, This will reduce the time spent for book development and their publication. The reason is that Artificial intelligence is designed to reduce the time required to complete a task.

Artificial intelligence is a useful tool for transforming ebooks into audiobook. For instance Apple and Google utilized Artificial intelligence to convert ebooks to audiobooks using a tool called text-to-voice technology, while other companies like DeepZen and Speechki are producing audiobooks using synthetic narration (Harris and Alter, 2020).

Academic publishing is an area where artificial intelligence can be useful for peer reviewing of journal articles, generation of abstracts and a whole manuscript. According to Wiwanitkit, & Wiwanitkit, (2024) Artificial intelligence can be utilised to transform various areas of academic publishing, which include scientific writing and peer review, generation of abstracts, introductions or even full manuscripts. Peer review process is the cornerstone of academic publishing, therefore using Artificial intelligence tools to accomplish this process will have significant impact on the quality (Duymaz & Tekin (2024) and the duration a journal takes to be produced. Additionally, Artificial intelligence can also assist automate certain

aspect of peer review, such as locating potential reviewers and doing preliminary evaluations of papers.

Using Artificial intelligence also has its negative side, for instance in academic publishing, the issue of dishonesty, plagiarism, authorship and the legitimacy of work, and over dependent on using Artificial intelligence tools are viewed by many scholars as inappropriate (Pereira, Reis & Santos, (2024), thereby reducing the ability of authors to think creatively and critically (Shofiah & Putera, nd). Consequently many scholars have strongly called for ethical code to prevent the misused of Artificial intelligence.

Another area where Artificial intelligence will affect the publishing industry is the loss of jobs, as many workers will be laid off, even though safe money for the industry, but the social and emotional toll on the people and their families and the society will be enormous (Acemoglu & Rescual, 2018). Even- though the introduction of Artificial intelligence will also create new jobs that will require new skills.

Challenges of Artificial Intelligence

The use of Artificial intelligence has huge benefits to the publishing industry, just as it does to many other industries, however there are also challenges that are associated with the use of this technology. According to Sytnyk (2024) Artificial intelligence presents challenges that are related to staff adaptation and overcoming technophobia. Since it is a new technology a lot of training on the use of Artificial intelligence will have to be embarked on to dispel fear in the minds of employees.

Liu (2023) pointed out that Artificial intelligence have impact in employment structure as traditional publishing jobs may be replaced by automation. Many jobs will be lost due to the application of Artificial intelligence in the publishing industry. However, no matter how creative the Artificial intelligence is, it can never be more creative than the humans who are its creator. Artificial intelligence as creative as it is will need the human inputs.

Liu, further stated that contents created by Artificial intelligence may be misused or abuse other people's, manuscript by infringing on copy right. Other challenges of Artificial intelligence in publishing industry are deskilling and degrading core academic activities, where human involvement is removed in editorial and reviewing roles. Publishers and authors may lose revenue as activities of pirates are likely to be on the increase as a resultant effect of the use of Artificial intelligence in publishing. Oguntayo at al. (2024) noted that with Artificial intelligence it is now easy to pirate, plagiarise and do other forms of infringement without having the hard copy or physically present in the territorial jurisdiction of the copyright owner.

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The study identified, content acquisition, providing information on market trends, checking on copyrights infringement, and editing as areas where Artificial intelligence is applicable in publishing. According to Publishers Association (nd) some of the most common application of Artificial intelligence in the publishing industry includes market trends to inform content acquisition, carrying out copyright infringement checks, running language and grammar checks, recommendation engines and demand forecasting to inform market strategy and identify relevant research.

Another area identified by the study, where Artificial intelligence can assist publishing are proofreading, peer review and in carrying out editorial duties by editors in the publishing industries. Publishers Association (nd) noted that Artificial intelligence is applicable in publishing in the area of content development. They further explained that apart from content development, Artificial intelligence can give assistance in proofreading, peer reviewing and in editorial texts.

Artificial intelligence is not only useful for proofreading but also for producing book and promotional materials. Society of Young Publishers (2024) observed that Artificial intelligence can be used to produce books, marketing materials, by drafting a social media post reminding people about an upcoming book releases

or author events or they can use the Artificial intelligence to design promotion materials.

Referencing is another area where Artificial intelligence can be applied in publishing. Referencing is an important aspect of content development and Artificial intelligence can greatly be used for this task (Afik et al, 2024). Every work cited in the text must appear in the reference page to avoid violating copyright laws. Artificial intelligence can assist publishers to provide reference page (s) of works cited in the text. According to Liebreuz M. & et al. (2023)“If prompted the system can deliver accompanying references.” Acknowledgment of every work cited in a book will save the author and the publisher from being dragged to court.

Readers and libraries select books that are of interest to them and their customers, this is where Artificial intelligence becomes useful to the audience. Artificial intelligence is a tool that can be used to select books that meet specific information needs of readers and library patrons. This way books that are published get to the right readers. Society of Young Publishers (2024) observed that Artificial intelligence has the capabilities of assisting readers in finding a wide range of books that suit their interest.

Plagiarism and intellectual property theft are issues bedeviling publishing in Nigeria and many developing countries. Author’s works have been copied without due acknowledgment, while authors and publishers have lost millions of naira, due to piracy because copyright laws were not fully enforced. With the coming of Artificial intelligence, the issue of plagiarism and copyright issue will be tackled. Artificial intelligence is also a tool that can be used to support editorial process in the publishing industry. According to Society of Young Publishers (2024) “AL can also offer support in the editorial process. Another frequently used AL tool is the plagiarism and copyright checker, which is useful for identifying peer reviewers and finding relevant research for authors.”

The contribution of Artificial intelligence to publishing in Nigeria can be in many ways. One such ways Artificial intelligence can contribute to publishing is by using it to generate contents of books. Onoja (2023) sees content creation as one of the

key areas where publishing can be assisted. He further urged that “AL powered writing tools are becoming increasingly popular, with businesses and industries and individuals using them to create everything from marketing copy to novels”

Publishing in Nigeria can be greatly assisted through the use of artificial intelligence serving as tool to improve the quality of the content of books to be published. Artificial intelligence can also improve efficiency and enhanced book production. In a survey conducted by Afolabi & Jimoh, (2024) on the use of artificial intelligence for publishing, 72% of the respondents said their use of Artificial intelligence had increased their efficiency and productivity, while Onoja wrote that Artificial intelligence can improve the quality of author’s work.

Artificial intelligence can provide assistance to Nigerian publishing houses in the efficient allocation of resources, improvement in the distribution of titles and in the translation of books into several Nigerian languages, reduce time for publishing a book and the financial cost required. Afolabi & Jimoh, (2024) urged that Artificial intelligence provide assistance to publishers by bringing efficiency into the operational aspect of publishing, resulting in efficient allocation of resources, and also facilitate the creation of titles in different languages that were previously inaccessible by readers.

Publishing houses in Nigeria can utilized Artificial intelligence to streamlining publishing process in content editing, proofreading, and content analysis, enhancing efficiency, enabling personalized marketing, predicting market trends, and optimising content strategies to better match reader’s preferences, ultimately improving the overall publishing experience for both authors and readers.

Artificial intelligence can also contribute to publishing in Nigeria by assisting publishing houses to generate more money through the production of both hardcopies and electronic copies of a book, thereby giving readers preference on the type of format they want the content. Mcllory, (2025) opine that, “AL is going to enable books morph into additional revenue-producing mediums, in ways we’ve never seen before.” This is a clever way for publishing houses in Nigeria to generate more revenue. Majival,(2015) asserted that there are no companies

today that can do without Artificial intelligence if they want to remain profitable and save money. Saving money means efficient use of resources and cutting down the cost of production. This also include reduction in personnel cost, fewer hands will be needed to accomplish task that Artificial intelligence cannot tackled. According to Schraagen & Diggleden (2021) “AI requires collaborative skills, such as being able to explain itself. On the other hand, the introduction of AL also results in a series of new skills that human experts need to develop in order to deal with AL”

Editors in book publishing industry in Nigeria and across the globe are faced with enormous task of ensuring that quality manuscripts are acquired, house styles are adhered to, sentencing and grammatical structures of content are in order and other task expected of the editors are performed before the manuscripts are eventually turned into books. The work of the editors, be it acquisition, copy, developmental and production editors (Dominick, 2009) can be simplified with the assistance of Artificial intelligence. Cutis (2023) is of the view that, artificial intelligence can be of help to editors, leading to reduction in workloads, Cutis further explained that editors are overwhelmed by the number of manuscript submission they received. Therefore deploying the use of Artificial intelligence will ease the burden placed on editors and publishers in the Nigerian publishing industry to meet deadlines. Editors in book publishing industry in Nigeria and across the globe are faced with enormous task of ensuring that quality manuscripts are acquired, house styles are adhered to, sentencing and grammatical structures of content are in order and other task expected of the editors are performed before the manuscripts are eventually turned into books

Findings/Results

The paper identified key areas where AI is useful in publishing, including referencing, proofreading, peer review, and editing. It also found that AI can generate book content, enhance content quality, support efficient resource allocation, improve title distribution, enable translation into Nigerian languages, reduce production costs and time, and boost revenue in the publishing sector.

Implications

The findings imply that both publishers and readers stand to benefit from the adoption of AI. While readers gain access to higher-quality books, publishers can experience increased efficiency and profitability. However, the integration of AI may also result in job displacement, which must be addressed to ensure a balanced impact

Conclusion

The study concludes that AI presents significant opportunities for the Nigerian publishing industry. It benefits both publishers and readers by improving content quality and increasing revenue. Nevertheless, the social implications, particularly the displacement of dedicated workers, cannot be ignored.

Recommendations

The study recommends that workers who lose their jobs due to AI implementation should be adequately compensated and retrained for new roles created by these technologies. This approach ensures that the publishing industry evolves in a sustainable and socially responsible manner.

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